

THE ROLE OF PARALINGUISTIC FEATURES IN SOCIAL MEDIA

Yusupova Dilnoza

First-year student, Arabic Philology Oriental University

Scientific advisor:

Turdiyev Jahongir

Associate Professor, Department of Languages-1

Annotation. This paper explores how paralinguistic features function in contemporary social media discourse and how they enhance the overall effectiveness of communication. It focuses on their role in minimizing ambiguity, avoiding misinterpretation, and reinforcing interpersonal interaction. Moreover, the study emphasizes the importance of paralinguistic components—such as emojis, GIFs and other visual symbols in fostering emotional engagement and increasing the efficiency of online communication.

Keywords: *paralinguistic features, social media platforms, digital communication, emojis, GIFs, communicative efficiency, nonverbal cues, emotional engagement.*

INTRODUCTION. The context of speech - including the proficiency levels of listeners and speakers, their behaviours during the communicative process, and the purpose of the utterance constitutes means beyond purely linguistic units. Accordingly, paralinguistic features, which accompany linguistic units during interaction, occupy a distinct place in spoken communication. Paralinguistics studies the bodily expressions that arise in speech situations, such as gestures, facial expressions and other corporeal movements. Paralinguistic resources perform an important function in communication and social interaction: when speech is delivered without their support, it tends to be less effective and the conveyed information remains dry. Paralinguistic elements are the virtual equivalents of voice tone, pauses, facial expression and gestures. Today, modern digital technologies and the development of social networks have produced new forms of social interaction. As communication tools, social networks have encouraged not only verbal but also paraverbal and nonverbal modes of expression. These resources serve to express emotional states, enrich meaning, and improve communicative effectiveness - and their investigation is a central task of paralinguistics (Jumanyazova, M. K., Annamuratova, S., 2025: 77).

REASERCHES. According to Knapp & Hall, vocal cues (paralanguage) such as tone, pitch, volume, and pauses contribute substantially to how messages are interpreted, shaping emotional meaning and relational impact beyond the words themselves (Knapp & Hall., 2010: Chapter 6) Danesi explicitly defines emojis, GIFs, and memes as forms of digital paralanguage, arguing that they function as visual substitutes for nonverbal cues by expressing emotion, stance, irony, and social alignment in online communication. (Danesi, Marcel., 2017: 45–52; 89–97). Li and Yang’s study provides empirical evidence that emojis serve crucial pragmatic and emotional functions in internet-based communication. Through corpus-based analysis, they show that emojis act as emotional stance markers, intensity enhancers, and interactional signals, compensating for the absence of vocal tone, facial expression, and gesture in written discourse (Li & Yang., 2018: 6–13).

REASERCH RESULTS. Research findings indicate that communication meaning is constructed not only through lexical content but also through paralinguistic and nonverbal resources that shape emotional interpretation, pragmatic force, and interpersonal relations. Empirical evidence from corpus-based studies demonstrates that emojis function as emotional stance markers, intensity enhancers, and interactional signals in internet-based communication, effectively compensating for the absence of vocal tone, facial expression, and gesture in written discourse (Li & Yang, 2018., 1-12). These findings align with Crystal's linguistic analysis of online communication, which emphasizes that non-standard orthographic features such as emoticons, expressive punctuation, and graphic variation serve as paralinguistic markers that replicate prosodic and affective cues traditionally present in spoken interaction (Crystal.,2001:89-101). Furthermore, Knapp and Hall's framework of nonverbal communication establishes that paralanguage — including tone, pitch, volume, and pauses — plays a decisive role in shaping listener perception, emotional resonance, and relational meaning beyond verbal content alone, particularly in interpersonal contexts (Knapp & Hall, 2010., 322-361). Taken together, these studies demonstrate that both vocal and visual paralinguistic resources operate as essential mechanisms for meaning-making, enabling speakers and writers to convey emotion, intention, and social alignment across face-to-face and digitally mediated communication environments.

As social networks have become a dominant form of communication, people are increasingly trying to express their thoughts and emotions not only through words but also through various additional means of expression. In this process, the role of paralinguistic elements has been steadily growing. On social media, such elements appear in forms that help convey emotional states more clearly and enhance the effectiveness of communication. Emojis and stickers are among the most widely used paralinguistic tools on social networks.

In conveying a message (SMS), respondents composing sentences with verbal language combinations and emoji in communicating ideas and expressing feelings. So even when they answer message from the receiver. The message is responded to and sent with a combination of verbal language and emoji. Other data sources also indicated that the respondents less agreed to convey with emoji. In the preparation of a sentence, emoji function to emphasize the message being delivered.(Arafah, B., & Hasyim, M.,2019: 494-504)

For example: Crystal illustrated in his book the two basic types express positive attitudes and negative attitudes respectively (the omission of the 'nose'element seems to be solely a functions)

- :-) or :) :- (or : (*
- :-) pleasure, humour, etc.*
- :- (sadness, dissatisfaction, etc.*
- ;-) winking (in any of its meanings)*
- ;- (: ~-(crying*
- %-(%-) confused*
- :-o 8-o shocked, amazed*
- :-] :-[sarcastic... (Crystal.,2001:36-37)*

And the GIF .GIF is a short, looping animated visual widely used in digital communication to express emotions, attitudes, and social intent that text alone cannot fully convey. In this article, the “please” penguin GIF functions as a paralinguistic device, visually signaling politeness, emotional appeal, and interpersonal stance. This interpretation aligns with the findings of Logi and Zappavigna (2024, pp. 32–56), who argue that GIFs operate as a form of social media paralinguistic, interacting with written text to convey emotion, stance, and social alignment. GIFs draw on shared cultural knowledge and visual semiotic resources, serving not merely as expressive add-ons but as integral communicative elements that amplify emotional meaning, clarify intent, and guide interpretation in digital interaction. As GIFs in social media posts act as a form of social media paralinguistic that interacts with written language to create meaning; through social semiotic multimodal discourse analysis of 100 posts from the X platform, they demonstrate that GIFs not only mirror the intermodal semiotic functions of emojis but also realise meaning through references to shared cultural knowledge, paralleling discourse semantics in the written co-text and forging inter- and intratextual connections that enrich digital communication. (Logi, L., & Zappavigna, M., 2024:32-56)

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, communication is not just about the words we use but how we use them. Paralinguistic shapes listener perception, emotional resonance, and relational meaning - aspects that cannot be captured by words alone. These features are especially relevant in fields such as interpersonal communication, psychology, and cultural studies, where the interpretation of meaning plays a central role in research and application.

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